

OSTE PILLAR FOREST FABRICATED BY DOUBLE REPLICA MOLDINGS OF LASER-CUT PMMA MOLD

Yuqian Yang, Zhiqing Xiao, Lexin Sun, Sihan Dai, Hao Yang,
Xingwei Zhang, Chia-Lin Sheu, and Weijin Guo

Shantou University, China

ABSTRACT

In this work, we developed a facile method to fabricate off-stoichiometry thiol-ene (OSTE) pillar forest by double replica moldings of laser-cut PMMA mold. The whole process is less than three hours, including the pattern design, PDMS molding, OSTE molding, cutting, and hydrophilic treatments. We can easily adjust the distance between micropillars, and the smallest side length of micropillars can reach $76\ \mu\text{m}$. The OSTE pillar forest can act as a porous substrate for capillary flow, and provide a flow rate as $1.35\ \mu\text{L/s}$ and $0.86\ \mu\text{L/s}$ for pitch distance of cutting lines as $350\ \mu\text{m}$ and $500\ \mu\text{m}$ respectively.

KEYWORDS: off-stoichiometry thiol-ene, OSTE, pillar forest, replica molding, PMMA, lateral flow tests, capillary pump, flow rate

INTRODUCTION

As one of the most representative technologies of point-of-care diagnostics, lateral flow tests has gained more and more attention. However, the current materials of lateral flow test substrates have some disadvantages, which limits the further application of lateral flow tests. Briefly, cellulose and nitrocellulose are limited by high variation in pore size and strong autofluorescence, and silicon pillar forest is limited by complex fabrication method and high cost. Here we come up with a facile method to fabricate OSTE pillar forest by double replica moldings of laser-cut PMMA mold. Compared to cellulose and nitrocellulose, OSTE pillar forest has uniform microstructure. Compared to silicon pillar forest, the fabrication method we proposed is much easier and the cost is also much lower. Moreover, we have already proved that polymer OSTE has very good optical properties including high optical depth and low autofluorescence [1]. In addition, it is easy to do hydrophilic treatments and protein immobilization on OSTE surface [2,3]. In short, OSTE pillar forest has high potential to be used as lateral flow test substrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Figure 1: The experimental procedures of OSTE pillar forest (a), the cutting pattern by laser cutter (b), the micro OSTE pillars ($p = 500\ \mu\text{m}$) under stereomicroscope (c), and micro OSTE pillars ($p = 350\ \mu\text{m}$) pictures by SEM (d-e). In (d), one pillar head is circled by a red rectangle for better visualization.

The experimental steps are shown in Figure 1(a). At first, we design the cutting pattern (as shown in Figure 1(b)), and cut PMMA plate ($11\ \text{cm} \times 11\ \text{cm}$) using a laser cutter: we cut the lines along X direction as the first step, then the lines along Y direction. Secondly, we use the PMMA mold to cast PDMS: we pour PDMS on PMMA mold, degas and cure it at $70\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for an hour. Thirdly, we use the PDMS piece as the mold to cast OSTE: we pour OSTE on PDMS mold, and cure it using flood UV exposure for 3 min. After we get the OSTE pillar forest piece, we cut it using a laser cutter to the shape of a lateral flow test strip, do the hydrophilic treatment using oxygen plasma, and

then cover the surface of test strip using a hydrophilic tape (as shown in Figure 2(a)). The long axis of test strip e-e' (shown in Figure 2(a)) is along the Y axis direction shown in Figure 1(b). We measure the volume capacity of water absorption on the test strip, and then investigate the flow behavior of water penetrating into the test strip. We use SEM and step profiler to investigate the surface morphology and microstructure dimension of OSTE pillar forest.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We tested two pitch distances of the cutting lines when designing cutting pattern (the parameter p shown in Figure 1(b)): 350 μm and 500 μm . We found that with 350 μm pitch distance, the average side length of pillars is 76 μm , and distance between pillars is ~ 274 μm . With 500 μm pitch distance, the average side length of pillars is 120 μm , and distance between pillars is ~ 380 μm . Since the intensity distribution of laser beam from the core to surrounding follows a Gaussian distribution [4], the profile of groove on PMMA and final OSTE piece is similar to a Gaussian curve, shown in Figure 1(a) (not to scale). The depth of groove is ~ 54 μm for p as 350 μm , and ~ 32 μm for p as 500 μm measured by a step profiler.

Figure 2: Design of the test strip, the picture of a test strip and the schematic of cross section of the test strip from top to down (a). The volume capacity of test strips with $p = 350$ μm and 500 μm (b). The flow behavior (volume versus time) on different test strips (c).

We measured the volume capacity by dipping the test strip into water vertically, observed the water penetration, and took it out when the penetration stopped. We measured the weight of test strip before and after water absorption, and calculated the volume capacity based on the weight of water absorbed (shown in Figure 2(b)). The volume capacity of test strip with $p = 350$ μm is 11.76 μL (6.32 $\mu\text{L}/\text{cm}^2$), and the volume capacity of test strip with $p = 500$ μm is 8.87 μL (4.76 $\mu\text{L}/\text{cm}^2$).

We tested the flow behavior by flowing water with color dye on the test strips, which were placed horizontally. We found that the flow behavior followed Washburn Equation (shown in Figure 2(c)). We used Washburn Equation for the fitting of experimental data, and got $R^2 > 0.99$ for $p = 350$ μm and $R^2 > 0.96$ for $p = 500$ μm . The average flow rates of these test strips are 1.35 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ and 0.86 $\mu\text{L}/\text{s}$ for $p = 350$ μm and 500 μm respectively, which are clinically relevant.

CONCLUSION

We developed an easy and fast way to fabricate pillar forest structure using a novel polymer OSTE, and studied its surface morphology and dimensions of the microstructure. We further investigated the flow behavior on OSTE pillar forest substrate, and proved that it can act as a capillary pump, and provide a clinically relevant flow rate. The uniform microstructure ensures the low variability of flow rates among test strips. It is very promising to use OSTE pillar forest as lateral flow test substrate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by Shantou University (STU Scientific Research Foundation for Talents: NTF20034).

REFERENCES

- [1] Guo et al. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* 163 (2020): 112279.
- [2] Zandi Shafagh et al. *ACS nano* 12.10 (2018): 9940-9946.
- [3] Guo et al. *Analytical chemistry* 92.9 (2020): 6194-6199.
- [4] Alda. *Encyclopedia of optical engineering* 999 (2003).

CONTACT

* Weijin Guo; guoweijin@stu.edu.cn; Yuqian Yang, Zhiqing Xiao, and Lexin Sun contribute equally to this work.